

FUZZY BASED UPFC SYSTEM FOR REDUCTION OF HARMONICS & LINE LOSSES

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ABSTRACT

Reduction of distribution system losses is of great significance in the present times. FACTS controller is discussed as the chosen system for this. The isolated salutation loop and multiple loop with the same structures are taken range for comparison analysis. By nullified line voltage rotation, many schemes have been evaluated to achieves minimize of loss. Current flowing through the loop algorithm sustainable compression is made over label. HP FC injection is necessary distribution loss to minimum for many loss minimization. Radial analysis are found to be single. Finally loss minimization using UPFC is implemented in simulation node. Many areas of applications is in impression phenomenon.

Index Terms— Distribution system, FACTS controller, Isolated distribution system, Loop distribution system, Compensation scheme, (UPFC).

1. INTRODUCTION

FACTS controllers show innumerable advantages including increase of power transfer capability, damping out power oscillations, stability improvement, etc. UPFC¹ is one such device which effectively accomplishes the above mentioned tasks. It is found out to be instrumental in reducing the voltage losses in case of the different configuration of distribution system. The transmission² and distribution system together are called bulk power system. Now days, the current trend in research is witnessing a gradual shift from transmission to distribution side and is mainly focused on distribution system owing to the fact that the losses in the distribution side are more. In Indian scenario, the distribution system losses are found be very high compared to other countries. These losses are generally unaccountable and incorporated in AT&C losses (Aggregate Technical Commercial losses)³. In some of the North-Eastern states, the AT&C losses across 50%, which means the power loss is half of the consumed power. For the purpose of conservation of energy, the